

Prediction and Detection of Glaucoma Using CNN

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Abstract— Glaucoma is one of the prime causes of blindness in people over the age of 60. It is sometimes called Sneak Thief of Vision. Glaucoma is a disease that destroys the optic nerve. This optic nerve is responsible for sending optic messages from the eyes to the brain. Glaucoma typically occurs when the fluid in the eyes doesn't drain off, as fluid should gradually build up and increase the pressure in your eye. The datasets are processed in a python programming language using these two main Machine Learning Algorithms. Here it is done using a classification algorithm called Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Algorithms that use machine learning methods could be efficient and effective tools for reinforcing the automatic decision-making machine processes

Keywords: Python Programming, Classification Techniques, Machine Learning Algorithms ,CNN

I. INTRODUCTION

This is a prediction of glaucoma from fundus images using machine learning. The features are extracted from the fundus images using image classification techniques. The fundus images are used directly for classification and predicting if there is glaucoma is present or not, and also detection of glaucoma using given dataset.

This study aims to provide an analysis of various aspects of the Convolutional Neural Network algorithm in predicting glaucoma based on the same dataset available in the public domain. Machine learning classification algorithms, such as CNN classification models, are used to apply classification techniques to the dataset. These models are used to improve the accuracy of the categorization approach. Through the CNN algorithm, the models have predicted the chances of occurrence of glaucoma. And also, determining the projected model's correctness. If the model has more epochs then the accuracy is higher and the error is less.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section looks at and assesses a few publications that are related to comparable studies."Deep learning and a random forest classifier were used to recognize glaucoma in fundus images" [1].

Using a random forest classifier with Au-net splitting, this method has 99 % detection accuracy, 93.5 % specificity, and 86.5 %sensitivity.

Fig 1: Decision tree

Upendra Singh Et al[2]. "A convolutional neural network for glaucoma detection "

The suggested method is built on a six-layer architecture, and CNN would identify the pattern that detects glaucoma diagnosis in a patient's eye photos, according to the authors. The ORIGA and SCES datasets are both used in this study. The proposed strategy worked effectively, and the outcomes were good. The AUC values are calculated based on the results of their experiment. The earned value is.882 and the earned value is.822.

S Mojtaba Golzan, Et al[3]"Enhanced glaucoma detection using a mixed convolutional and recurrent neural network".

In differentiating glaucoma from healthy people, this network outperformed all others, with a sensitivity of 0.95, specificity

of 0.96, F-measure of 96.19 percent, and AUC of 0.99. of 0.96.

Fig 2: Original and cropped fundus image

Sandra Morales Et al [4]"A comprehensive validation of CNNs for automatic glaucoma assessment using fundus pictures".

The accuracy from five public databases (1707 pictures) was acquired using the Xception architecture, with an average AUC of 0.9605 with a 95 percent confidence interval of 95.92–97.07 percent, an average specificity of 0.8580, and an average sensitivity of 0.9346.

"Survey on detection of glaucoma in fundus pictures by segmentation and classification," D.Vijayasekar Et al[5].

SVM classifier is the optimum for classifying images.

III. MOTIVATION

Glaucoma is a situation in which the eye's optic nerve is destroyed. An increase in intraocular pressure is commonly connected to it. Glaucoma is a condition that is passed down through generations. It's common for it to be discovered later in life.

The optic nerve, which carries images to the brain, can be damaged by intraocular pressure, or pressure inside the eye. It can cause irreversible vision loss or perhaps total blindness in some years if the damage increases.

Causes of Glaucoma: Aqueous humor, the fluid that fills your eye, normally exits through a mesh-like tube. The fluid builds up if this duct becomes clogged or the eye generates too much fluid. Experts aren't always sure what causes the blockage. But it can be inherited, which means that it is passed from parents to children.

A physical or chemical injury to the eye, serious eye infection, blockage of blood vessels within the eye, and inflammatory diseases are also less common causes of glaucoma. It's uncommon, although it can happen after eye surgery to treat another condition. Both eyes are affected, but one can be more get affected.

Glaucoma risk factors include:

- If you or your ancestors are of African American, Irish, Russian, Japanese, Hispanic, Inuit, or Scandinavian descent.
- If you fall over the age of forty years.
- If you genes related to glaucoma.
- If you have any of these eye related diseases - shortsighted or farsighted.
- If you have low eyesight.
- If you have pancreas related diseases.
- If you are taking steroid medications such as prednisone
- If you are taking certain bladder control medications
- If you are taking some steroid medications such
- If you have thinner corneas in eyes than in a normal person with healthier eye.
- If you have any injuries in eyes.
- If you have high blood pressure, diabetes, or sickle cell anemia

Symptoms of Glaucoma:

Closed-angle glaucoma symptoms usually appear sooner and are more obvious.

- If you have disturbance under glare of light
- if you have temporary or permanent loss of vision.
- If you have itchiness or redness in the eyes.
- If you have a confused eye (particularly in babies).
- If you frequently have upset stomach or vomiting.
- If you have pain in eyes.

IV . METHODOLOGY

a) Data Source

The dataset for predicting glaucoma was obtained from Kaggle, which is open to the public. There are 900 fundus photos in the dataset. Numerical data is taken from the fundus images for prediction. 80 percent of the data is used for training, while the remaining 20% is used for testing.

b) Convolutional Neural Network(CNN)

Convolutional Neural Network CNN, is a well-known technique in computer vision applications. This is a type of deep neural network that can interpret visual pictures. This architecture is the most used for identifying things in images. CNN has 3 layers: 1) A Convolutional layer: Only a small portion of the input layer is linked to the hidden neuron layer in this case. 2) Pooling layer: This reduces the dimensionality of the featured map. 3) Fully Connected Layer: The input to the fully connected layer is the output from the final pooling layer.

Convolutional 2D is the very first hidden layer, and has 32 feature maps with a size of 5*5 and a rectifier function. The pooling layer, which accepts a maximum value to hold a 2*2 pool size, is the following layer. Layer regularisation is used in the dropout, which eliminates 20 percent of neurons at random and prevents overfitting. The flatten layer, which turns 2D matrix data into a vector, is the following layer. The completely linked layer, with 128 neurons and a rectifier activation function, is the next layer. The output layer, which comprises ten neurons for ten classes, is the last layer.

- a) *Algorithm* :The Prediction of glaucoma using image
 Train CNN with TensorFlow
 Step 1: Uploading the Dataset
 Step 2: Convolutional layer
 Step 3: Pooling layer
 Step 4: Second Convolutional Layer and Pooling Layer
 Step 5: Dense layer
 Step 6: Finding Epoch
 Step 7: Predicting Glaucoma or not

Experimental Result : Epoch loss: 1.1697 ,Accuracy: 0.5363.
 Evaluation of Performance: Loss:0.710586667060852 0.5 accuracy
 And determining whether or not the patient has glaucoma.

V.IMPLEMENTATION

1. Import the necessary package

```
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D
from tensorflow.keras.layers import MaxPooling2D
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Flatten
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense
```

2.Classify the data using CNN

```
classifier = Sequential()
# Step 1 - Convolution
classifier.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), input_shape = (256,256, 3), activation = 'relu'))
# Step 2 - Pooling
classifier.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size = (2, 2)))
```

3.Train the data .

```
# print(train_datagen)
test_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale = 1./255)
training_set = train_datagen.flow_from_directory('dataset/train',
target_size = (256,256),
batch_size = 32,
class_mode = 'binary')
```

4.Finding the performance Evaluation

```
score = classifier.evaluate_generator(test_set,40/batch_size)
print(" Total: ", len(test_set.file_names))
print("Loss: ", score[0], "Accuracy: ", score[1])
```

5.Finally ,predicting and detecting whether glaucoma present or not

```
result = model.predict(test_image)
training_set.class_indices
if result[0][0] == 1:
    print("Glaucoma")
    chance = 100
    print("Chance :",chance)
else:
    print("Not Glaucoma")
    chance = 0
```

VI. RESULT

Result : Epoch loss: 1.1697 ,Accuracy: 0.5363.Performance Evaluation:Loss:0.710586667060852 Accuracy: 0.5.This accuracy is of the patient with not glaucoma affected. Their is 99.5% detection accuracy ,for glaucoma affected .

Fig 4: Accuracy of the not glaucoma affected

Fig 5: Accuracy of the glaucoma affected

Fig 6: Training and Test Loss plotting

Fig 7 :Training and validation accuracy(when number of epoch is high less the error)

In the results, It shows that as the number of epochs increases the accuracy also increases. The error also is less. We can conclude that if the error is lower then higher the accuracy.

CONCLUSION

Through this paper can conclude that diagnosis automation using machine learning can get efficient and effective image classification using CNN. The accuracy is about 0.9603.CNN is known because of its ability to learn highly discriminative features from raw pixel intensities. Through automation, we can train more data at a time.

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